

ON A BEAM ON ELASTIC FOUNDATION ANALYSIS MODEL FOR SANDWICH SCB TEST SPECIMEN

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Keywords: Sandwich, Debonding, Fracture toughness, SCB, Elastic foundation, Analysis

ABSTRACT

To theoretically analyze the compliance and the energy release rate of the sandwich single cantilever beam (SCB) test specimen, an analysis model named 'beam on Vlasov foundation model' was proposed in the previous research. However, the core at the cracked portion (cracked core) of the sandwich SCB test specimen is not taken into account in the model. In this study, the effect of inclusion of a cracked core on the analysis results of a beam on Vlasov foundation model is investigated. It is found that the analysis model which takes the cracked core into account gives an excessively stiff solution contrary to its theoretical consistency. Including the cracked core in addition to the assumption that the in-plane displacement in the core is fixed to zero may give excessively stiff conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures, where two thin face sheets made from stiff and strong material such as metal or fiber reinforced plastic are bonded to a thick lightweight material called core, are attractive for use in weight-critical applications such as aerospace structures, naval structures and wind turbine blades. Although sandwich panels have superior mechanical properties, their performance depends on the integrity of the interfacial bond between the face sheet and the core. Thus, the face/core debonding failure has received much attention in the literature [1-4]. Since the fracture toughness is considered to be minimum for mode I loading, several debond fracture tests under mode I type loading have been proposed [5]. Among these mode I type debond fracture tests, the single cantilever beam (SCB) test has attracted attention as the best candidate for evaluating the face/core debond fracture toughness under mode I type loading [6-9].

To theoretically analyze the compliance and the energy release rate of the sandwich debond fracture toughness test specimens under mode I type loading (including the sandwich SCB test specimen), a beam on Winkler foundation model, which was originally developed by Kanninen [10] to analyze an isotropic double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen, has been proposed [11-13]. In the model, the upper debonded face sheet is considered as a beam and the core supporting the face sheet at the bonded part is represented by Winkler type elastic foundation. However, when using the Winkler foundation model, the extensional modulus of the Winkler foundation has to be provided as an analysis parameter. Although several definitions of the Winkler foundation modulus for the sandwich debond fracture toughness test specimens have been proposed [11-13], their theoretical bases are weak. To overcome the problem, Yoshida [14] and Yoshida and Aoki [15] proposed a beam on Vlasov foundation model, where the modified Vlasov method [16-19] was applied to a beam on elastic foundation analysis for sandwich debond fracture toughness test specimen. In the model, the foundation moduli are not provided as analysis parameters but derived through the variational principle used in the theory of elasticity. The validity of the model for the analysis of sandwich SCB test specimen was confirmed by comparing with the finite element analysis [15]. However, Yoshida and Aoki [15] applied the beam on elastic foundation model only on the uncracked portion and

ignored the core at the cracked portion (cracked core) of the sandwich SCB test specimen. Ignoring the cracked core is considered inappropriate from the viewpoint of theoretical consistency. In this study, regarding a beam on Vlasov foundation model for a sandwich SCB test specimen, the effect of inclusion of the cracked core on the analysis results is investigated.

2 A BEAM ON VLASOV FOUNDATION ANALYSIS

2.1 General description of an analysis

Fig.1 shows the sandwich SCB test specimen. The face sheets and the core have thicknesses t_f and t_c , respectively. The overall length of the specimen, the crack length and the length of the uncracked portion are represented as l , a and c , respectively. In this paper, the sandwich SCB specimen is treated as a linear elastic body in a two-dimensional plane stress state and the width of specimen is set to be unit length (1 mm). It is assumed that the core consists of an isotropic material such as a foamed plastic core. Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus of the core are expressed as E_c , ν_c and G_c , respectively. The elastic constant of the core defined as $F_c = E_c/(1-\nu_c^2)$ is also used. It is assumed that the face sheet also consists of an isotropic material in this study for simplicity. The Young's modulus of the face sheet is expressed as E_f .

Figure 1: Single cantilever beam (SCB) test specimen.

(a) Built-in beam

(b) Deflection and rotation at crack tip

Figure 2: Calculation of loading point deflection.

The compliance of the SCB test specimen C is defined as $C = \delta/P$, where P is the applied load and δ is the deflection at the loading point as shown in Fig.1. Let the distance from the loading point to the

crack tip be the crack length a . The procedure for representing C as a function of a is described below. When analyzing the deflection δ by beam models, the sum of deflections shown in Fig.2(a) and Fig.2(b) should be calculated. $\delta_{(a)}$ in Fig.2(a) means the deflection at the loading point when assuming the cracked upper face sheet is rigidly fixed at the crack tip. While, $\delta_{(b)}$ in Fig.2(b) means the deflection at the loading point due to the deflection and the slope of deflection of upper face sheet at the crack tip (w_{tip} and θ_{tip}), which are caused by the deformation of core, and $\delta_{(b)}$ is evaluated as follows:

$$\delta_{(b)} = w_{\text{tip}} + \theta_{\text{tip}} a \quad (1)$$

The deflection $\delta_{(a)}$ can be relatively easily obtained using an elementary beam theory. On the other hand, in order to calculate the deflection and slope of deflection at the crack tip, w_{tip} and θ_{tip} , a beam on elastic foundation model was proposed [15]. In the model, the face sheet is modeled as a beam and the core is treated as an elastic foundation as shown in Fig.3. However, the core at the cracked portion of the specimen, which is specified as a 'cracked core' in Fig.3, was not taken into consideration. In this study, analysis which includes the cracked core is also conducted and its effect is investigated.

Figure 3: Beam on elastic foundation model.

2.2 Analysis without cracked core

When ignoring the cracked core, the area $x < 0$ in Fig. 3 is ignored and only the area of $x \geq 0$ is analyzed. First, displacements of the elastic foundation in x and z directions are denoted by \tilde{u} and \tilde{w} respectively and assumed as follows:

$$\tilde{u}(x, z) = 0, \quad \tilde{w}(x, z) = w(x)\psi(z) \quad (2),(3)$$

where $\psi(z)$ is referred to as the attenuation function, which satisfies the boundary conditions as follows:

$$\psi(0) = 1, \quad \psi(-t_c) = 0 \quad (4),(5)$$

In Eqs.(2) and (3), it is assumed that the displacement \tilde{u} is negligibly small compared to \tilde{w} . And the deflection function of the beam is set to be identical to the function $w(x)$ in Eq.(2), based on the assumption that the displacement in the z direction of the elastic foundation at $z = 0$, i.e. $\tilde{w}(x, 0) = w(x)$, is identical to the deflection of the beam. The governing equations and the boundary conditions of $w(x)$ and $\psi(z)$ are derived from the principle of minimum potential energy. The potential energy is expressed as follows:

$$\Pi = U_{\text{beam}} + U_{\text{found}} - W_{\text{load}} \quad (6)$$

where U_{beam} and U_{found} are the strain energy stored in the beam and the foundation, respectively and W_{load} is the work done by the external load, that can be expressed as follows:

$$U_{\text{beam}} = \int_0^c \frac{1}{2} E_f I_f \left(-\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx \quad (7)$$

$$U_{\text{found}} = \int_0^c \int_{-t_c}^0 \left(\frac{1}{2} F_c \varepsilon_z^2 + \frac{1}{2} G_c \gamma_{xz}^2 \right) dz dx = \int_0^c \int_{-t_c}^0 \left\{ \frac{1}{2} F_c w^2 \left(\frac{d\phi}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} G_c \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 \phi^2 \right\} dz dx \quad (8)$$

$$W_{\text{load}} = \bar{Q} w \Big|_{x=0} - \bar{M} \frac{dw}{dx} \Big|_{x=0} \quad (9)$$

I_f is the moment of inertia of the cross section of the upper face sheet beam and is given by $I_f = t_f^3/12$. Thus, $E_f I_f$ represents the flexural stiffness of the upper face sheet beam. It is assumed that the length of the non-cracked part c is sufficiently larger than the core thickness t_c and thus the condition of $w \rightarrow 0$ when $x \rightarrow \infty$ is satisfied. Then, $\delta \Pi = 0$ gives the governing equation of $w(x)$ as shown below,

$$E_f I_f \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} - k_\theta \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + k_w w = 0 \quad (x \geq 0) \quad (10)$$

and the boundary conditions of $w(x)$ at $x = 0$ as follows:

$$E_f I_f \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} = \bar{M} \quad , \quad E_f I_f \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} - k_\theta \frac{dw}{dx} = \bar{Q} \quad (11),(12)$$

k_w and k_θ in Eq.(10) and Eq.(12) are constants determined by $\psi(z)$ as follows:

$$k_w = F_c \int_{-t_c}^0 \left(\frac{d\psi}{dz} \right)^2 dz \quad , \quad k_\theta = G_c \int_{-t_c}^0 \psi^2 dz \quad (13),(14)$$

Moreover, $\delta \Pi = 0$ gives the governing equation of $\psi(z)$ as follows:

$$\frac{d^2 \psi}{dz^2} - \left(\frac{\xi}{t_c} \right)^2 \psi = 0 \quad (15)$$

where ξ is the non-dimensional parameter defined by using $w(x)$ as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\xi}{t_c} \right)^2 = \frac{1 - \nu_c}{2} \frac{\int_0^c (dw/dx)^2 dx}{\int_0^c w^2 dx} \quad (16)$$

And $\psi(z)$ should satisfy the boundary condition shown in Eqs.(4) and (5).

It is noted that the functions $w(x)$ and $\psi(z)$ are coupled in Eqs. (10)-(16). Considering the couplings, the functions $w(x)$ and $\psi(z)$ are solved by the following procedure. First, an initial trial value of ξ is set in Eq.(15) and then the attenuation function $\psi(z)$ is obtained from Eq. (15) with Eqs. (4) and (5) as follows:

$$\psi(z) = \begin{cases} 1 + (z/t_c) & (\xi = 0) \\ \frac{\sinh \left[\xi \{1 + (z/t_c)\} \right]}{\sinh \xi} & (\xi > 0) \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Then, $\psi(z)$ is used in Eqs.(13) and (14) to calculate k_w and k_θ . Using these k_w and k_θ in Eqs.(10), (12) and considering the condition that $w \rightarrow 0$ when $x \rightarrow \infty$, the deflection function $w(x)$ is obtained from Eqs.(10)-(12). Then, $w(x)$ is used in Eq.(16) to re-evaluate ξ . This procedure is repeated until ξ converges to a constant value. When treating k_w , k_θ and ξ as constants, the solutions of the differential equations (10) and (15) can be easily obtained and thus the above procedure can be easily executed.

Eq.(18) shows the deflection of the upper face beam $w(x)$ obtained from the procedure described above:

$$w(x) = \frac{P}{E_f I_f} \frac{1}{\eta_1} e^{-\beta x} \left[\{(\beta^2 + \gamma^2)\gamma a + 2\beta\gamma\} \cos \gamma x - \{(\beta^2 + \gamma^2)\beta a - (\beta^2 - \gamma^2)\} \sin \gamma x \right] \quad (18)$$

where

$$\beta = \sqrt{\sqrt{\frac{k_w}{4E_f I_f} + \frac{k_\theta}{4E_f I_f}}}, \quad \gamma = \sqrt{\sqrt{\frac{k_w}{4E_f I_f} - \frac{k_\theta}{4E_f I_f}}} \quad (19),(20)$$

and

$$\eta_1 = \gamma(\beta^2 + \gamma^2)(3\beta^2 - \gamma^2) \quad (21)$$

The deflection and the slope of deflection at crack tip ($w_{\text{tip}} = w|_{x=0}$ and $\theta_{\text{tip}} = -(dw/dx)|_{x=0}$) can be obtained from Eq.(18). Then, the deflection δ_{b} can be obtained by substituting these w_{tip} and θ_{tip} into Eq.(1).

2.3 Analysis with cracked core

In order to take into account the cracked core, the procedure presented in Sec.2.2 should be modified as follows.

As for the potential energy, Eq.(8) should be replaced by Eq.(22) which includes the region of $x < 0$ in the integration range:

$$U_{\text{found}} = \int_{-a}^c \int_{-t_c}^0 \left\{ \frac{1}{2} F_c w^2 \left(\frac{d\phi}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} G_c \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 \phi^2 \right\} dz dx \quad (22)$$

It is assumed that both the length of cracked core a and the length of non-cracked part c are sufficiently larger than the core thickness t_c , and that the condition of $w \rightarrow 0$ when $x \rightarrow -\infty$ in addition to the condition of $w \rightarrow 0$ when $x \rightarrow \infty$ is satisfied. After Eqs.(7), (9) and (22) are used in Eq.(6), $\delta \Pi = 0$ gives the governing equation and the boundary conditions of $w(x)$ as shown in Eqs.(10)-(12) but Eq.(12) should be replaced by Eq.(23):

$$E_f I_f \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} - k_\theta \frac{dw}{dx} + \sqrt{k_\theta k_w} w = \bar{Q} \quad (23)$$

Eqs.(13) and (14) which define the constants k_w and k_θ are not modified and are used as they are. $\delta \Pi = 0$ also gives the governing equation of $\psi(z)$ as shown in Eq.(15). It is noted that Eq.(16) should be replaced by Eq.(24) which includes the region of $x < 0$ in the integration range:

$$\left(\frac{\xi}{t_c} \right)^2 = \frac{1 - \nu_c \int_{-a}^c (dw/dx) dx}{2 \int_{-a}^c w^2 dx} \quad (24)$$

Through the same iteration procedure as described in Sec.2.2, the deflection of the beam $w(x)$ can be obtained as follows:

$$w(x) = \frac{P}{E_f I_f} \frac{1}{\eta_2} e^{-\beta x} \left[\{(\beta^2 + \gamma^2)\gamma a + 2\beta\gamma\} \cos \gamma x - \left\{ (\beta^2 + \gamma^2) \left(\beta + \sqrt{2(\beta^2 - \gamma^2)} \right) a - (\beta^2 - \gamma^2) \right\} \sin \gamma x \right] \quad (25)$$

where β and γ are evaluated by the same Eqs.(19) and (20) as used in Sec.2.2. It is noted that η_2 shown below in Eq.(26) instead of η_1 of Eq.(21) is included in Eq.(25).

$$\eta_2 = \gamma(\beta^2 + \gamma^2) \left\{ 3\beta^2 - \gamma^2 + 2\beta\sqrt{2(\beta^2 - \gamma^2)} \right\} \quad (26)$$

Then, the deflection δ_b can be obtained by substituting w_{tip} and θ_{tip} which are calculated from Eq.(25) into Eq.(1).

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed to evaluate the validity of the analysis which uses beam on Vlasov foundation model. Two-dimensional finite element models of sandwich SCB specimens were constructed using eight-node quadrilateral plane-stress elements in the commercial program MSC Marc Mentat as shown in Fig.4. The shape of all elements excluding those around the crack tip was set to be a square with a side of 0.5 mm and the fine meshes were used around the crack tip so that the minimum element dimension at the crack tip was 0.03 mm. The crack was inserted just at the interface between the upper face sheet elements and the core elements. Linear elastic analyses were carried out to compute the compliance of the sandwich SCB specimen.

Figure 4: Finite element analysis model.

4 RESULT

Dimensions of the sandwich SCB test specimen which are specified in Fig.1 were set as $l=200\text{mm}$, $t_f=2\text{mm}$ and $t_c=50\text{mm}$. Both the face sheet and the core were assumed to be isotropic materials and the material properties of $E_f=100\text{GPa}$, $\nu_f=0.3$ and $E_c=100\text{MPa}$, $\nu_c=0.25$ were used. Fig.5 shows analysis results of the compliance with various crack lengths in the range of $5\text{mm}<a<70\text{mm}$. The result of finite element analysis (FEA) is also shown in Fig.5. Results of analysis model without cracked core agrees very well with FEA results. However, analysis model including cracked core gives excessively stiffer results compared to FEA.

Figure 5: Compliance of sandwich SCB test specimen.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, regarding a beam on Vlasov foundation model for a sandwich SCB test specimen, the effect of inclusion of the core at the cracked portion (cracked core) on the analysis results is investigated in detail. It is found that the analysis model which takes the cracked core into account gives an excessively stiff solution contrary to its theoretical consistency. Including the cracked core in addition to the assumption that the in-plane displacements in the core is fixed to zero may give excessively stiff conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP19K04845.

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